

YIELD OF WINTER WHEAT DEPENDING ON ROOT AND FOLIAR NUTRITION OF PLANTS

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ABSTRACT

The article presents the results of scientific research and their proposals regarding the influence of mineral fertilizer and Rosalik PK + ME microfertilizer on the morphological indicators of winter wheat of the Doridna variety. For the use of mineral fertilizers with the norm $N_{70}P_{45}K_{75}$ in combination with Rosalik microfertilizer PK+ME with the norm 2.0 l/ha, which ensured the grain yield of winter wheat at the level of 51.4 t/ha of good quality.

Keywords: winter wheat, variety, fertilizers, morphological indicators.

Formulation of the problem. Winter wheat is an important agricultural crop in Ukraine, which is key in the agricultural sector [1].

Cereal grain is the main food material in various industries. Exactly, grain quality is the – main tool that is so necessary for nutrition [2, 5, 8]. Its area of crops today reaches more than half of all sown areas, namely grain crops. Because Ukraine is one of the leading exporters of wheat in the world [3, 6].

The soils and weather conditions of Polissia are favorable for obtaining high yields of winter wheat and producing high-quality grain. In addition, winter wheat for crops such as sugar beet, legumes are the best precursor [4]. In order to have a good yield, it is necessary to provide the crop with fertilizer and adhere to the correct cultivation technology in relation to the set deadlines and sowing rates. The climatic conditions of the area and the fertilization system have been shown to be the main factors that influence the yield of winter wheat [1, 7].

Analysis of recent research and publications.

The use of mineral fertilizers to form the yield of winter wheat can quickly decrease when dry conditions arise in the territory of its cultivation [4, 8]. And it is under such conditions that there is a need to regulate fertilizer doses and their terms for the use of mineral fertilizers depending on the reserve of productive moisture in the farm's soils [2, 4].

Microfertilizers are one of the most effective means that affect the productivity of winter wheat and the quality of its products. There are about 30 important trace elements that are vital for plants and animals [2].

With a lack of trace elements in the plant, the destruction of reproductive organs and tissues begins, chlorosis appears on the leaves, shoots, roots and growth points die.

And all this leads to a significant decrease in yield [3].

Therefore, it is the fertilization system that requires generalization and knowledge, since there are many different scientific results of research that have been conducted in different climatic zones of the country and are controversial regarding fertilization [7].

The purpose of research. To establish the yield of winter wheat and the qualitative characteristics of the harvest of the Doridna variety depending on the root (NPK) and foliar (NPK + Rosalik PK + ME) nutrition of plants.

Research results. We analyzed the results of research on the cultivation of winter wheat of the Doridna variety during 2022-2024.

According to the research results, the morphological indicators of winter wheat were influenced by the use of mineral fertilizers and Rosalik PK + ME microfertilizer, which in turn had a positive effect on the yield of Doridna wheat (table 1).

Table 1

The effect of fertilization on the number of stems and the height of winter wheat plants of the Doridna variety, average for 2022-2024.

Research options	Total number of stems, pcs./m ²	Total number of productive stems, pcs./m ²	Height of winter wheat plants, sm
1. Control (without fertilizers)	468	433	87,9
2. $N_{70}P_{45}K_{75}$	506	486	91,1
3. $N_{70}P_{45}K_{75}$ + Rosalik microfertilizer PK + ME	517	499	94,5
$NIR_{0,5}$, pcs./m ² , cm	20,1	15,7	2,2

For the use of mineral fertilizers $N_{70}P_{45}K_{75}$ (option 2), the total number of plant stems was 506 pieces/m², which is more than the control variant (without fertilizers, option 1 - 468 pieces/m²) by 38 stems.

With additional application of Rosalik PK + ME microfertilizer (option 3), the number of stems increased to 517 pieces/m², or 49 pieces/m² more than the option without fertilizers (control). The difference was significant, as $NIR_{0,5}$ was equal to 20,1 pcs/m².

The same pattern was observed for the total number of productive stems. The difference in fertilized options reached 53-66 pieces/m² compared to the control, for $NIR_{0,5}$ – 15,7 pieces/m², which had a positive effect on grain yield.

During the application of mineral fertilizers and additional application of Rosalik PK + ME microfertilizer, the characteristics of the quality indicators of wheat grain of the Doridna variety changed (table 2).

Table 2

Bakery qualities of winter wheat grain of the Doridna variety average for 2022-2024

Research options	Grain nature indicators, g/l	Weight of 1000 wheat grains, g	Gluten content indicators, %	Protein content indicators, %
1. Control (without fertilizers)	729	39,1	22,7	11,9
2. $N_{70}P_{45}K_{75}$	732	42,6	21,9	12,8
3. $N_{70}P_{45}K_{75}$ + Rosalik microfertilizer PK + ME	735	42,9	21,6	13,4

When applying fertilizers, the weight of 1000 grains increased. In the non-fertilizer variant (control), it was equal to 39,1 grams, for the use of mineral fertilizers – 42,6 grams, and the additional use of Rosalik microfertilizer PK + ME – 42,9 grams, or 3,5 grams and 3,8 grams more control, respectively.

The gluten content of wheat grain decreased from the application of mineral fertilizers and reached 21,9%, compared to the option without fertilizers (control) – 22,7% for the use of Rosalik microfertilizer PK + ME –.

It should be noted that the amount of protein increased with the use of fertilizers. If in the version without fertilizers (control) its amount was within 11,9%,

then when applying $N_{70}P_{45}K_{75}$ it increased to 12,8%, and when applying Rosalik microfertilizer PK + ME - to 13,4%, or 1, according to the control version increased by 0,9% and 1,5%.

The yield of winter wheat grain was significantly affected by the application of fertilizers. Due to the use of both mineral fertilizers and the additional use of Rosalik PK + ME microfertilizer to mineral fertilizers, the yield of wheat grain and its quality indicators increased significantly, which is reflected in our research (table 3).

Table 3

Yield of winter wheat of the Doridna variety average for 2022-2024

Research options	Wheat yield, c/ha	Increase in wheat harvest	
		c/ha	%
1. Control (without fertilizers)	34,4	-	-
2. $N_{70}P_{45}K_{75}$	43,2	8,8	125
3. $N_{70}P_{45}K_{75}$ + Rosalik microfertilizer PK + ME	51,4	17,0	149
$NIR_{0,5}$, c/ha	5,8	-	-

In the control version (without fertilizers, option 1), grain yield within 34,4 c/ha was obtained, for the use of only mineral fertilizers at the rate of $N_{70}P_{45}K_{75}$ (option 2), the yield increased to 43,2 c/ha, and for the additional application of Rosalik microfertilizer PK + ME (option 3) to mineral fertilizers - up to 51,4 c/ha.

A substantial increase in yield was obtained in comparison with the control variant, respectively, by 8,8 c/ha and 17,0 c/ha for $NIR_{0,5}$ – 5,8 c/ha.

That is, the application of mineral fertilizers in combination with Rosalik PK + ME microfertilizer allows you to obtain a high yield of winter wheat grain, which proves the high efficiency of this fertilization.

Conclusions. The results of the studies confirm that when growing winter wheat of the Doridna variety, it is recommended to use mineral fertilizers with the

norm $N_{70}P_{45}K_{75}$ in combination with Rosalik microfertilizer PK+ ME with the norm 2,0 l/ha as fertilizer, which ensures grain yield at the level of 51,4 c/ha of good quality.

References

1. Korotkova I. V., Horobets M. V., Chaika T. O. The influence of growth stimulants on the productivity of spring barley varieties. Bulletin of the Poltava State Agrarian Academy. 2021. №2. S. 20–30.
2. Simonenko N. IN. Protein content in the grain of winter rye varieties (*Secale cereale* L.) and its inheritance by hybrids. Colloquium journal. 2022. №4(127). P.31–35.
3. Mazur V. A., Palamarchuk V. D., Polishchuk I. S., Palamarchuk O. D. The latest agricultural technologies in crop production. Vinnytsia, 2017. 588 p.

4. Yu. Klipakova. O., Priss O. P., Bilousova Z. V., Yeremenko O. A. Yield of winter wheat depending on pre-sowing seed treatment. *Bulletin of Agrarian Science*. 2019. №4. S. 16–23.

5. Kudrya S. I., Kudrya N. A., Zvonar A. M. Effect of winter wheat precursor on soil nutrient content. *Bulletin of the Center for Scientific Support of APV of the Kharkiv region*. Kharkiv. 2017. Vol. 23. S. 37–47.

6. Cherednychenko I. IN. Agroecological indicators for different levels of biologicalization of agriculture. *Guide of a Ukrainian farmer*. 2016. T. 1. S. 110–111.

7. Petrychenko V.F., Lykhochvor V.V. Crop production. *New technologies for growing field crops: textbook. 5th, corrigendum., add.* Lviv: NVF «Ukrainian technologies», 2020. 806 p.

8. Tribel S. O., Strygun O. O. Plant protection – the real direction of increasing the production of plant products. *Protection and quarantine of plants*. 2013. №. 59. S. 324–336.